

Database

- MySQL
- RQG tests
- SQL

Debugging

- Code tracing
- Reproduce the bug

Project specific concepts

- Code base
- Documentation
- GIMP project
- GUI Facebook
- Project UI
- Pygame project
- VLC documentation

Testing

- Diagnostics tests
- Testing environment
- Unit testing

Programming concepts

- Button
- Concurrency
- Error handling
- Files handling
- Graphics design
- Graphics programming
- Image processing
- Menu
- Modal dialog
- Object Orientation
- Parser
- Privacy
- Reactive
- Shortcuts
- String handling
- Threads
- Tooltip
- UI coding
- Unicode
- Usability
- Video programming
- Web programming

Operating infrastructure

- Apache server
- Compilers
- Deployment
- Git
- GNOME
- Hardware components
- HTTP protocols
- Input/Output
- Installation
- Internet of things
- Linux
- Linux Kernels security's common capability
- Mac OS X
- Memory consumption
- Memory handling
- Memory mapping input/output
- Network
- NPROC
- Operating systems design
- Preloaded Public Key Pinning
- Runtime monitoring (watch data flow)
- Security
- Software backup files
- Ubuntu
- wxGTK 3.0x (build system)

Programming languages

- C
- C++
- Differences between Python 2.7 and 3
- HTML & CSS
- Java
- Javascript
- PHP
- Python
- Vala
- XML

Program comprehension

- Code comprehension
- Code parsing
- Ohloh analysis
- Software analysis
- Static analysis

Project architecture

- Adopted Design patterns
- Architecture (how a component works: buffer)
- Browser interacts with customized settings and plugins
- Component of the project: input data reading
- Configuration files
- External packages that are used and their syntax/functionality
- Level of customer service
- Project structure

External Libraries

- DX10,DX11
- ggit-1.0 library
- glib-2.0 library
- Gravatar
- GTK.ScrolledWindow
- GTK+
- GTKBuilder
- Libmetis libraries
- Redshift GTK